

Familiarity and complexity of a movement influences motorimagery in dancers: A cross-sectional study

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ABSTRACT

The present study aimed to analyze the differences between ballet, contemporary, and flamenco dancers when generating mental motor kinesthetic and visual images of simple and complex movements. A cross-sectional study, including 45 professional dancers (15 flamenco dancers, 15 ballet dancers, and 15 contemporary dancers), was planned. We analyzed the ability to generate mental motor visual and kinesthetic images with the revised movement imagery questionnaire (MIQ-R) and mental chronometry (MC); the real movement execution (RME) chronometry was also measured, using arm and jump movement assessments. ANOVA revealed significant differences between groups regarding the jump movement assessments for the kinesthetic MIQ-R item ($F = 5.29$, $P = 0.009$), for the RME chronometry ($F = 13.19$, $P = <0.001$), and for the kinesthetic MC ($F = 9.28$, $P < 0.001$). The post-hoc analysis revealed significant differences between flamenco dancers compared with contemporary and ballet dancers for all the variables regarding the jump movement. Flamenco dancers used significantly greater visual than kinesthetic imagery modalities to generate mental motor imagery in the jump movement ($P = 0.024$, $d = 0.63$). No differences were found in the arm movement assessment between groups. Results reveal differences in the ability to generate motor images, specifically the kinesthetic ones, between flamenco dancers and ballet and contemporary dancers. When performing a non-familiar complex movement, dancers predominantly use a visual motor imagery modality, which leads to a longer execution time as well as a longer time for kinesthetic mental motor imagery.

KEYWORDS

action familiarity, dance, motor imagery

1. INTRODUCTION

Mental practice is a cognitive reproduction of a motor action used for promoting learning and improving motor tasks.¹ The use of mental practice, and specifically mental imagery, is frequently employed in dance as a tool to optimize motor performance² and also to provide a neural process for creation and optimization of movement sequences within artistic expression.^{3,4}

Several types of mental imagery used in dance have been described.^{2,5,6} There is evidence that motor imagery might improve the motor performance of technical movements executed by dancers.^{7,8} Furthermore, motor imagery might modulate the anatomical properties of the trunk to maintain stability and improve cushioning in dancers with low back pain history.⁹

Motor imagery is defined as a mental rehearsal of movements without their actual execution,¹⁰ and within motor imagery, there are two variants: visual and kinesthetic. Visual motor imagery is described as a process of visually imagining oneself performing a motor task (third-person imagery), and kinesthetic imagery is the process of somatosensory simulation of performing a motor task (first-person imagery).¹¹ From a neurophysiological point of view, it has recently been reported that both imagery modalities (visual and kinesthetic) share similar neuronal networks.¹²

In professional dancer populations, contradictory results have been found regarding the predominant type of mental imagery used. Some authors have found dancers present a greater ability to generate visual images than non-dancers,¹³ and other authors have found a predominance of kinesthetic imagery or even a combination of both visual and kinesthetic approaches.¹⁴ On the other hand, visual or kinesthetic motor imagery could

have a specific function depending on the gesture or movement performed by the dancer.^{14,15}

Understanding the specific motor imagery modalities used by dancers according to the various styles of dance could have a crucial repercussion on motor learning of dance movements and new sequences of choreographed movements, and it could also help improve rehabilitation modalities for injured dancers.

With the evidence we currently have, we cannot draw clear conclusions regarding this specific issue, and further research is necessary. The main hypothesis of this research is that the type of motor imagery modality employed and the ability to generate visual and kinesthetic motor images it is going to be different between groups of dancers regarding the imagined movement. Therefore, our primary aim was to identify whether there were differences between ballet, contemporary, and flamenco dancers when generating mental motor kinesthetic and visual images of simple and complex gestures.

As a secondary aim, we compared the time taken to generate the mental motor images and to execute the actual movement between the three dancer groups, and whether these two variables were related to each other.

2. METHODS

Study design

A cross-sectional study design with a non-probabilistic sample was used to assess the ability to generate mental motor images and to compare mental chronometry and actual motor execution chronometry among the different styles of professional dance. The design followed the international recommendations for Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology (STROBE).¹⁶ All participants received an explanation of the study procedures, which were planned according to the ethical

standards of the Declaration of Helsinki and approved by the Ethics Committee of the Centro Superior de Estudios Universitarios La Salle with the registration number CSEULS-PI-170/2017. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants before their inclusion.

Participants

A non-probabilistic sampling by convenience consisting of professional dancers was performed between June 2017 and February 2018, from a Higher Conservatory of Dance. Various dance disciplines were accepted, including flamenco dancers (FD), contemporary dancers (CD), and ballet dancers (BD).

Participants were selected if they met all of the following inclusion criteria: (a) professional dancers and (b) men and women between the ages of 18 and 30 years.

The exclusion criteria were as follows: (a) presence of pain at the time of the study; (b) injured dancers without current professional activity; (c) having previously participated in a similar study; (d) presence of vestibular, ocular, or postural deficiencies; and (e) an incomplete understanding of Spanish.^{9,15,17}

Procedure

After having agreed to participate, all included participants received a sociodemographic questionnaire to complete on the day the measurements were performed. The questionnaire contained questions regarding age, sex, and marital status. Then, each participant completed a series of self-reported measures to assess their ability to generate kinesthetic and visual mental motor images and mental chronometry. Finally, motor execution chronometry of the task was assessed.

Outcome measures

a. Visual and kinesthetic ability to generate mental motor images

To assess the ability to generate mental motor images, a modified reduced version of the revised movement imagery questionnaire (MIQ-R) was used. The original questionnaire has four repeated movements in two subscales, one visual and one kinesthetic. The MIQ-R has adequate internal consistencies with an acceptable Cronbach's alpha (0.84 for the entire scale, 0.80 for the visual subscale, and 0.84 for the kinesthetic subscale).¹⁸

In this modified version (*mMIQ-R*), only two tasks of the original questionnaire (items 2/5 and items 3/8) were used and each mental task was performed twice (Figure 1A), once in a visual form and once in a kinesthetic form:

Jump movement

The first motor imagery task chosen was a jump movement, which is a very specific movement of professional dancers. The movement was to bend down and then jump straight into the air as high as possible with both arms extended above the head (Figure 1C). This movement corresponds to items 2 (visual form) and 5 (kinesthetic form) of the MIQ-R questionnaire.

Arm gesture

The second task chosen was an arm gesture, a very elementary gesture, to observe possible differences with the first specific task. The movement consisted of extending the arm of the non-dominant hand of the subject in a straight line outwards, parallel to

the ground, with the palm of the hand sidedown. Then, move the arm forward until it is directly in front of the body, keeping it extended and parallel to the ground, and execute the movement slowly (Figure 1B). This movement corresponds to items 3 (kinesthetic form) and 8 (visual form) of the MIQ-R questionnaire.

After actually performing the movement, each item is scored on a 7-point scale, where 1 indicates “very difficult to see/feel” and 7 indicates “very easy to see/feel”, in the same way as the MIQ-R questionnaire.

b. Mental chronometry

The time dedicated to imagine each task was recorded using a stopwatch. The recorded time corresponded to the interval between the command to start the task (given by the evaluator) and the verbal response at the conclusion of the task (given by the participant). Mental chronometry (MC) is a reliable measure that has been widely used to record objective measures of the ability to imagine.¹⁹⁻²¹

c. Real movement execution

After the motor imagery task, the participants were asked to perform the real movement execution (RME) of the task, and the time dedicated to perform each task was recorded using a stopwatch. During motor imagery, spatial and temporal information are similar to those of the physical execution, suggesting that the time taken to imagine the movement would be similar to that needed for its real execution. Thus, comparing the time taken to perform the motor task and the mental task should provide substantial information about the ability to preserve spatial and temporal organization during motor imagery and could reliably be used to measure the temporal congruence between real and imagined movements.^{20,22}

Sample size calculation

The sample size was calculated to detect differences between the groups regarding the results of the primary variable (ability to generate mental motor images). To perform the calculation, a pilot study was previously conducted with 15 participants (three groups of five dancers). The ability to generate motor images with the MIQ-R (specific jump movement) was compared between the three groups using ANOVA *t* test. There were statistically significant differences, and the effect size was large ($\eta^2 = 0.22$). Using a statistical power of 80% (1- β probability of error) and a probability of error level α of 0.05, we generated a total sample size of 45 participants (15 per group). The software for calculating the sample size was G*Power 3.1.7 for Windows (G*Power[®], University of Dusseldorf, Germany).²³

Statistical analysis

We employed the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS 22, SPSS Inc, Chicago, IL, US) for the statistical analysis. The level of significance for all tests was $P < 0.05$.

In the data analysis, we used descriptive statistics to show the data on the continuous variables, which are presented as mean and standard deviation (SD), 95% confidence interval (95% CI), and relative frequency (percentage). We employed the χ -squared test to compare differences between the categorical variables (nominal). The Shapiro-Wilk test was used for the normality tests. We applied analysis of variance (ANOVA) as a statistical test to compare the continuous variables between groups. A three-way ANOVA was used to assess the interaction between activity and group. A multiple comparison Bonferroni post-hoc enabled comparison of the differences in terms of the

ability to generate mental images, MC (visual and kinesthetic MC), and motor execution chronometry (RME chronometry). Partial eta-squared (η^2) was calculated as a measure of effect size (strength of association) for each main effect and interaction in the ANOVAs, with 0.01-0.059 representing a small effect, 0.06-0.139 a medium effect and >0.14 a large effect.²⁴

We calculated the effect size (Cohen's *d*) to compare the study variables. Based on the Cohen method, the effect was considered small (0.20-0.49), medium (0.50-0.79), or large (>0.8).²⁵ The relationship between the visual and kinesthetic ability to generate images and the time needed to perform the mental and real motor task was analyzed using Pearson's correlation coefficient. A Pearson correlation coefficient >0.60 indicated a strong correlation, a coefficient between 0.30 and 0.60 indicated a moderate correlation, and a coefficient <0.30 indicated a low correlation.²⁶

3. RESULTS

A total of 45 professional dancers were included in the study, and they were assigned to three balanced groups consisting of 15 participants each: flamenco dancers (FD) ($n = 15$), contemporary dancers (CD) ($n = 15$), and ballet dancers (BD) ($n = 15$). There were no statistically significant differences in the sociodemographic data between groups (Table 1). No adverse events or dropouts were reported in any of the groups.

Arm gesture

The ANOVA revealed no significant changes between groups ($P > 0.05$). There were no significant differences in kinesthetic and visual MIQ-R item score ($F = 2.81$ and $F =$

2.16, respectively, $P > 0.05$), visual and kinesthetic MC ($F = 0.53$ and $F = 0.88$, respectively, $P > 0.05$) and in the RME chronometry ($F = 0.43$, $P = 0.65$) between groups.

Jump movement

The ANOVA revealed significant changes in the kinesthetic MIQ-R item ($F = 5.29$, $P = 0.009$) between groups. The post-hoc analysis revealed significant differences between the flamenco dancer group compared with the contemporary ($P = 0.039$, $d = -0.84$) and ballet dancer groups ($P = 0.014$, $d = -1.07$), with a large effect size.

The ANOVA also revealed significant changes in kinesthetic MC ($F = 9.28$, $P < 0.001$) between groups. The post-hoc analysis revealed significant differences between the flamenco dancer group compared with the contemporary ($P = 0.007$, $d = 1.13$) and ballet dancer groups ($P = 0.001$, $d = 1.40$), with a large effect size.

In addition, the ANOVA revealed significant changes in the RME chronometry of the jump movement ($F = 13.19$, $P < 0.001$) between groups. The post-hoc analysis revealed significant differences between flamenco dancers compared with contemporary ($P < 0.001$, $d = 1.90$) and ballet dancers ($P < 0.001$, $d = 1.49$) with a large effect size (Figure 2).

No significant differences were found between groups in visual MIQ-R item scores ($F = 1.53$, $P = 0.228$) and visual MC ($F = 0.45$, $P = 0.64$).

Imagery modality

The results obtained showed significant differences in the *m*MIQ-R score between groups. The ANOVA revealed significant changes during group*activity ($F = 3.53$, $P = 0.038$, $\eta^2 = 0.144$). The results showed that flamenco dancers used a significantly greater

visual than kinesthetic imagery modality to generate mental motor imagery in the jump movement, with a moderate effect size ($P = 0.024$, $d = 0.63$). There were no statistically significant intra-group differences in either contemporary or ballet dancers ($P > 0.05$). The post-hoc analysis also showed inter-group significant differences between flamenco dancers compared with both contemporary and ballet dancers with a large effect size (Table 2). The total scores for mMIQ-R and mental chronometry are shown in Table 3.

Multiple comparisons

In the assessment of the interaction group*activity through a three-way ANOVA in relation to the jump movement, statistically significant differences were obtained between groups ($F = 4.74$, $P = 0.002$, $\eta^2 = 0.184$).

In the assessment of the interaction group*activity through a three-way ANOVA in relation to the arm gesture, no statistically significant differences were obtained between groups ($F = 1.48$, $P = 0.214$, $\eta^2 = 0.066$).

Psychometric properties

Internal consistency was calculated to report reliability data. Cronbach's alpha was used as an index of internal consistency for the total test score. Test consistency was acceptable at $\alpha = 0.726$ in terms of the total test score.

Correlation analysis

Regarding the jump movement, the main correlations were found for the contemporary and ballet dancer groups, in which strong, positive associations were found between the ability to generate kinesthetic mental motor images and the ability to generate visual mental motor images ($r = 0.71$ and 0.84 , $P < 0.001$, respectively).

In addition, there was a strong negative association in the flamenco dancer group between the kinesthetic MC and the RME chronometry ($r = -0.76, P < 0.001$). Finally, strong negative associations were found in the contemporary dance group between the RME chronometry and both kinesthetic and visual ability to generate mental motor images ($r = -0.73$ and $-0.76, P < 0.001$), respectively (Table 4).

In relation to the arm gesture, the main correlations were found in the contemporary and ballet dancer groups in which strong positive associations were found between the ability to generate kinesthetic mental motor images, and the ability to generate visual mental motor images ($r = 0.70$ and $0.85, P < 0.001$), respectively. In the contemporary and ballet dancer groups, strong negative associations were also found between the visual MC and the ability to generate visual mental motor images ($r = 0.66$ and $0.66, P < 0.001$, respectively). Finally, there was a strong negative association in the flamenco dancer group between RME chronometry and the ability to generate visual mental motor images ($r = -0.74, P < 0.001$; Table 5).

4. DISCUSSION

The primary aim of this research was to compare the type of motor imagery modality and the ability to generate visual and kinesthetic motor images between ballet dancers, contemporary dancers, and flamenco dancers, regarding a simple movement and a complex one. We also analyzed the time of execution of the movement and the time taken to generate mental motor images as well as the association between the variables. The results reveal differences in the ability to generate motor images, specifically the kinesthetic ones, between flamenco dancers and ballet and contemporary dancers, but not between ballet dancers and contemporary dancers. We found that Flamenco dancers

presented a predominantly visual modality to imagine the jump, and they needed longer to perform it as well as to generate the kinesthetic image compared with the other groups. The time taken to perform the movement and to generate the mental images was similar among the three groups, with strong and moderate associations between those variables.

Motor imagery modality

In this research, we analyzed a simple upper extremity movement and a jump that was a more complex motor gesture. Among the upper extremity movements, we found no statistically significant differences between any of the measured variables, nor in the time taken for the imagery, the actual performance of the movement performance, or in terms of imagery modalities used. However, for the complex movement (the jump), differences were found among the kinesthetic image generation modalities between groups. Flamenco dancers present a lesser ability to generate kinesthetic mental images; we hypothesize that this finding could be due to the Flamenco dance itself, in which jump training and practice is not as common as it is among contemporary or ballet dance. It was further observed that Flamenco dancers used a visual modality more than a kinesthetic one for this movement. We hypothesize that when flamenco dancers are asked to perform and imagine a motor task not used in their professional discipline, the planning of the movement takes longer than it does for other dancers, and the flamenco dancers needed a visual resource to approach a new or non-habitual movement. Previous evidence has suggested that visual motor imagery is predominant when the action requires the reproduction of a form by drawing, and kinesthetic imagery is predominant when the action requires precise coordination or timing.¹¹

On the other hand, it is important to highlight that the motor imagery modality appears to depend on the type of movement, its complexity, or on previous experience performing

it, as Olsson and Nyberg suggest.¹⁰ Other authors propose that the modality used depends on the aim of the movement or the expected result. In other words, if the motor task needs precise kinematics properties for its correct execution, kinesthetic motor imagery would be beneficial, but if the final outcome of the action is more important, a visual modality could be more efficient.²⁷

It is important to keep in mind that among dancers, visual or kinesthetic motor imagery interventions could have a specific effect on the task required, and the combination of both modalities is recommended to obtain the most benefit in terms of the improvement of motor skills.⁷

Considering our results, we suggest that familiarity with the movement is a crucial condition to take into account when imagining a motor movement. We observed no differences between ballet dancers and contemporary dancers in the jump movement, noting that in these two dance disciplines, jumping is a habitual movement, whereas it is not habitual in flamenco dance. However, for the simple motor gesture, there were no differences when generating motor images among the three groups. In relation to this, Rieger demonstrated that familiarity with an action promotes the generation of more precise motor images, which occurs when stable cortical representations of an internal action have been acquired.²⁸

Time used to generate motor images and to execute the movement

In the intra-group comparison, the time used to execute the movement the upper extremity movement and the jump, and for visual and kinesthetic motor image generation, was similar for the three groups of dancers. There were no differences between mental activity and the execution of the motor gesture, as described in previous studies.²⁸⁻³²

We found two differences in the comparison between groups, which were that flamenco dancers took longer than ballet and contemporary dancers to perform the execution of the jump and to generate the mental kinesthetic images. This difference might be due to the familiarity with the gesture, as mentioned earlier. The need to perform a movement that includes some difficulty requires more complex network processing to plan the execution, whereas a familiar movement or artistic gesture involves integrated, broad, inherent, kinesthetic network processing. Guillot and Collet have suggested that the perception of the difficulty of the task can also influence the chronometry of the generation of motor mental images, leading athletes to overestimate the chronometry for the imagined movements. These authors also propose that in automatic or cyclic motor gestures, the chronometry is similar for execution and for mental image generation. However, when the movement is complex, it is necessary to use greater attention resources, leading to a longer chronometry for mental motor image generation.¹⁹ Other researchers have reported an increase in the perceived difficulty of the movement can generate an inverse effect on the time needed for mental image generation.^{29,33} An additional aspect to mention is that flamenco dancers needed more time to generate kinesthetic motor images than the other two groups, which was also found in previous research performed with other populations.^{34,35} Based on those previous results, it has been suggested that there is greater difficulty in evaluating somatosensory signals than visual ones when forming motor images.²² In contrast, however, Féry et al¹¹ suggest that the use of kinesthetic motor images are more effective for learning a movement than are visual motor images.

Study of associations

In the correlation analysis, positive associations of a moderate to strong magnitude were obtained between the time taken to generate motor images and the time taken for the execution of the real movement; previous studies found results similar to ours.^{21,28} It should be noted that the strongest correlations appeared between the execution of the movement and the generation of kinesthetic images in the three groups. In addition, moderate to highly negative associations were observed between the ability to generate mental motor images and both the chronometry for motor image generation and the real execution of the movement. A similar result was obtained by Zhang et al,³⁷ in which a negative association was found between the vividness of kinesthetic images and temporal congruence, in contrast to what Williams et al²¹ found.

Limitations

One limitation of our study is the fact that the analyzed “complex” movement is a familiar movement only for two groups of dancers but not for the third (flamenco dancers); it would be interesting to analyze the behavior of flamenco dancers exposed to a familiar complex movement, to see whether the predominance of visual modality would shift toward a kinesthetic or combined modality; and on the other hand, if the present results would be maintained if ballet and contemporary dancers were exposed to an unfamiliar movement.

Perspective

Currently, neuroscience in sports medicine has had relatively little impact on understanding of how dancers learn and generate mental motor images involving body posture and alignment.³⁸ This gap in understanding is due, in part, to the tendency for

studying motor skills to use simple tasks.³⁹ However, emerging evidence suggests that when such tasks are replaced by more challenging activities involving multiple effectors, such the chosen in the present research, richer insights into motor imagery processes may be obtained. In addition, Moran et al, 2001 argued that it is necessary a greater knowledge of chronometric measures of motor imagery as well as the different motor imagery modalities used in order to better understand of motor learning in sports.⁴⁰ In this regard, our results have shown the specific motor imagery modalities used by dancers according to the various modalities of dance, and it have a potential impact on the way it is understood the motor learning, as well as in the motor imagery use as a tool for to optimize motor performance.

Future randomized clinical trials

The results of the present study demonstrated that dancers use different motor imagery modalities and take different amounts of time to generate motor mental images depending on the movement performed. However, it is necessary that future studies continue to explore mechanisms of mental practice in dancers. Comparing the ability to generate images between professional and amateur ballet dancers would be interesting for future studies in relationship with our results. In addition, it could be relevant to analyze whether the selection of the modality depends only on the familiarity or unfamiliarity with the assessed movement or if the dance discipline or specific training also has significant influence. Finally, it is necessary that future studies continue investigating the neurocognitive bases of mental practice in dancers, and how it could be used to improve the acquisition of new motor sequences or its possible role in rehabilitation processes.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The results of this study demonstrate that dancers use different motor imagery modalities depending on their familiarity with the gesture assessed, and that dancers also differ in the time needed to execute the movement and the time needed to generate the motor mental kinesthetic images.

When performing a non-familiar complex movement, dancers predominantly use a visual motor imagery modality, which leads to a longer execution time as well as a longer time for kinesthetic mental motor imagery of that unfamiliar gesture. This phenomenon was observed in flamenco dancers, with the assessment based on a jump as the complex unfamiliar movement, compared with ballet and contemporary dancers, for whom a jump is a highly familiar movement.

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TABLES

TABLE 1. Descriptive statistics of sociodemographic data

Measures	FD (n = 15)	CD (n = 15)	BD (n = 15)	P-value
Age (y)	24.2 ± 2.3	24.2 ± 1.8	23.4 ± 1.4	0.170
Practice time (y)	19.2 ± 2.4	18.8 ± 1.6	18.3 ± 1.5	0.326
Gender				0.757
Male	7 (46.7)	5 (33.3)	6 (40)	
Female	8 (53.3)	10 (66.7)	9 (60)	

Values are presented as mean ± standard deviation or number (%).

BD: Ballet Dancers group; CD: Contemporary Dancers group; FD: Flamenco Dancers group.

TABLE 2. Comparative analysis regarding the imagery strategy to generate mental motor images in the jump gesture

Measure	Group	MIQR-V	MIQR-K	Mean difference (95% CI); Effect size (<i>d of Cohen</i>)
<i>m</i> MIQ-R	FD	6.00 ± 0.92	5.33 ± 1.17	0.66* (0.09 to 1.23); <i>d</i> = 0.63
	CD	5.80 ± 1.47	6.20 ± 0.86	-0.40 (-0.97 to 0.17); <i>d</i> = -0.33
	BD	6.47 ± 0.64	6.33 ± 0.61	0.13 (-0.70 to 0.44); <i>d</i> = 0.22
Mean difference (95% CI); Effect size (<i>d of Cohen</i>)	FD vs CD	0.02 (-0.75 to 1.17); <i>d</i> = 0.16	-0.86* (-1.69 to -0.03); <i>d</i> = -0.84	
	FD vs BD	-0.46 (-1.44 to 0.51); <i>d</i> = -0.08	-1.00* (-1.83 to -0.16); <i>d</i> = -1.07	
	CD vs BD	-0.66 (-1.64 to 0.31); <i>d</i> = -0.14	-0.13 (-0.96 to 0.69); <i>d</i> = -0.17	
Measure	Group	MC-V	MC-K	Mean difference (95% CI); Effect size (<i>d of Cohen</i>)
MC	FD	2.80 ± 0.70	3.38 ± 0.76	-0.58* (-1.01 to -0.14); <i>d</i> = -0.79
	CD	2.58 ± 0.70	2.64 ± 0.52	-0.05 (-0.49 to 0.37); <i>d</i> = -0.09
	BD	2.85 ± 1.02	2.45 ± 0.55	0.40 (-0.03 to 0.83); <i>d</i> = 0.48
Mean difference (95% CI); Effect size (<i>d of Cohen</i>)	FD vs CD	0.21 (-0.53 to 0.97); <i>d</i> = 0.31	0.74* (0.17 to 1.02); <i>d</i> = 1.13	
	FD vs BD	-0.05 (-0.80 to 0.70); <i>d</i> = -0.05	0.93* (0.36 to 1.49); <i>d</i> = 1.40	
	CD vs BD	-0.27 (-1.02 to 0.48); <i>d</i> = -0.30	0.18 (-0.38 to 0.75); <i>d</i> = 0.35	

BD, Ballet Dancers group; CD, Contemporary Dancers group; CI, confidence interval; FD, Flamenco Dancers group; MC, Mental Chronometry; MC-K, Time employed in Kinesthetic item; MC-V, Time employed in Visual item; MIQR-K, Kinesthetic item; MIQR-V, Visual item; *m*MIQ-R, modified Revised Movement Imagery Questionnaire.

**P* < 0.05.

TABLE 3. Comparative analysis regarding the total score

Measures	FD (n = 15)	CD (n = 15)	BD (n = 15)	P-value
mMIQ-R	22.86 ± 2.97	24.53 ± 3.35	25.93 ± 2.15	0.020*
MIQR-K	10.66 ± 2.16	12.33 ± 1.63	12.86 ± 1.06	0.002*
MIQR-V	12.20 ± 1.74	12.20 ± 1.85	13.06 ± 1.16	0.249
MC (s)	11.56 ± 2.18	10.78 ± 1.66	10.89 ± 2.15	0.525
MC-K	5.96 ± 1.17	5.67 ± 1.09	5.16 ± 1.06	0.145
MC-V	5.59 ± 1.33	5.11 ± 1.11	5.73 ± 1.65	0.438

Values are presented as mean ± standard deviation or number (%).

BD, Ballet Dancers group; CD, Contemporary Dancers group; FD, Flamenco Dancers group; MC, Mental Chronometry; MC-K, Time employed in Kinesthetic items; MC-V, Time employed in Visual items; MIQR-K, Kinesthetic items; MIQR-V, Visual items; mMIQ-R, modified Revised Movement Imagery Questionnaire; s, seconds.

* $P < 0.05$.

TABLE 4. Correlation analysis in the jump gesture

Measures	Group	MC-K	MC-V	MIQR-V	MIQR-K	RME
MC-K	FD	-	0.66**	-0.09	-0.61*	-0.76**
	CD		0.19	-0.52*	-0.58*	-0.61*
	BD		0.21	-0.34	-0.30	-0.59*
MC-V	FD		-	-0.33	-0.22	-0.56*
	CD			-0.42	-0.49	-0.43
	BD			-0.75**	-0.74**	-0.59*
MIQR-V	FD			-	-0.06	-0.06
	CD				0.71**	-0.76**
	BD				0.84**	-0.61*
MIQR-K	FD				-	-0.64*
	CD					-0.73**
	BD					0.56*

BD, Ballet Dancers group; CD, Contemporary Dancers group; CI, confidence interval; FD, Flamenco Dancers group; MC, Mental Chronometry; MC-K, Time employed in Kinesthetic item; MC-V, Time employed in Visual item; MIQ-R, Revised Movement Imagery Questionnaire; MIQR-K, Kinesthetic item; MIQR-V, Visual item; RME, Real Movement Execution.

* $P < 0.05$

** $P < 0.001$

TABLE 5. Correlation analysis in the arm gesture

Measures	Group	MC-K	MC-V	MIQR-V	MIQR-K	RME
MC-K	FD	-	0.48	-0.36	-0.39	-0.57*
	CD		-0.11	-0.24	-0.01	-0.54*
	BD		0.32	-0.27	-0.31	-0.59*
MC-V	FD		-	-0.36	-0.11	-0.59*
	CD			-0.66**	-0.58*	0.03
	BD			-0.66**	-0.41	0.45
MIQR-V	FD			-	0.08	-0.74**
	CD				0.70**	-0.54*
	BD				0.85**	-0.60*
MIQR-K	FD				-	-0.54*
	CD					-0.17
	BD					-0.47

BD, Ballet Dancers group; CD, Contemporary Dancers group; CI, confidence interval; FD, Flamenco Dancers group; MC, Mental Chronometry; MC-K, Time employed in Kinesthetic item; MC-V, Time employed in Visual item; MIQR, Revised Movement Imagery Questionnaire; MIQR-K, Kinesthetic item; MIQR-V, Visual item; RME, Real Movement Execution.

* $P < 0.05$.

** $P < 0.001$

FIGURES

FIGURE 1. Representation of the movements used for the imagery procedure and motor execution. A, Motor imagery representation. B, Arm gesture. C, Jump movement

FIGURE 2. Differences in chronometry and real execution of the jump gesture. MC-K, Time employed in Kinesthetic item of Mental Chronometry; MC-V, Time employed in Visual item of Mental Chronometry. RME, Real Movement Execution. *P < 0.05; **P < 0.001